

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF INTRODUCING CHILDREN WITH NATURE

Rajabova Iroda Hamidovna

Associate Professor, Bukhara State University.

Umarova Maftuna Ko'klam kizi

Student of group 9-6 MTS-20.

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Abstract. *The pedagogical process aimed at ensuring the comprehensive development of children in MTT is complex, but also diverse. To achieve educational effectiveness, it is necessary to properly organize each type of activity in the organization. This article describes the use of modern technologies in conducting nature education activities and their effectiveness.*

Keywords: *nature, method, innovation, STEAM, SMART, activity, center, creative work.*

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЗНАКОМСТВА ДЕТЕЙ С ПРИРОДОЙ

Аннотация. *Педагогический процесс, направленный на обеспечение всестороннего развития детей в МТТ, сложен, но и многообразен. Для достижения образовательной эффективности необходимо правильно организовать каждый вид деятельности в организации. В данной статье описывается использование современных технологий при проведении природообразовательных мероприятий и их эффективность.*

Ключевые слова: *природа, метод, инновация, STEAM, SMART, деятельность, центр, творческая работа.*

The economic power of each country, the rise in the level of socio-spiritual life are determined by the competitiveness of the education system, the development of science. Therefore, the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan sets as priority tasks the radical improvement of the education sector, the improvement of the quality of education, the formation of an intellectually capable, physically fit generation, in-depth training in exact sciences, and the training of qualified personnel for various sectors of the economy, ultimately providing for the creation of an education system that can meet the demands of today.

As a result of reforms in the sector, the management mechanism in the preschool education system has been radically improved, the system of non-state educational services has been reformed, the system of secondary specialized and vocational education has been revised, measures have been strengthened to improve the quality of training of specialists with higher education, and a two-stage system of postgraduate education has been introduced.

Technologies and methods of introducing children to nature.

The tasks facing the educator in introducing children to the world around them:

1. Formation of an elementary system of knowledge in children.

The system of knowledge about nature includes knowledge about its objects and phenomena (their characteristics, properties, as well as connections and relationships between them.

2. Formation of work skills and abilities in children.

Work skills and abilities acquired in childhood are not destroyed - in the future they are improved, turning into more complex types of work.

3. Formation of love for nature in children.

A caring attitude towards nature involves the manifestation of good deeds and actions in those cases when it is necessary, and for this children should know how to care for plants, what conditions to create for their favorable growth and development. Of particular importance for the formation of a caring attitude towards nature is knowledge about a living organism, the ability to distinguish it from objects of inanimate nature.

It is very important to develop curiosity, inquisitiveness, creativity and research activities in all aspects of children's education. Children's experimental research activities are of great importance in the implementation of this task. The study of this activity increases the personal experience, skills and qualifications of preschoolers, allows them to collect knowledge about the phenomena and processes occurring in the living and inanimate nature around us, and at the same time to learn the properties of objects. That is why students of pedagogical higher educational institutions, especially future teachers, should be closely familiar with the scientific and practical situation of children's experimental research activities.

A good knowledge of children's experimental-research scientific and practical activities allows the future educator to properly organize the education of children.

Children's experimental-research is one of the main forms of children's research activities, which is directed towards a specific goal, has a self-developing effect on the formation and development of motivation, and directs children to additional knowledge. Its main advantage is that it provides children with information about various aspects of the object being studied, about its relationship with the environment, nature. In the process of experimentation, the child's memory is enriched, their thinking processes are activated, since the need arises to carry out the processes of analysis and synthesis, comparison, classification and generalization. Experience and experimentation itself involve an active search for ways to solve problems, making assumptions, putting hypotheses into practice, and drawing conclusions. That is, experience and experiments play an important role in the intellectual development of preschool children.

Content of knowledge, skills and abilities when introducing children to the world around them. In the junior group, it is important for children to accumulate knowledge, that is, specific ideas, about individual objects of nature: about natural material (sand, water, snow, ice) and its properties, about the structure of plants (stem, leaf, flower) and their needs for moisture, about the appearance of animals (fish, birds, mammals and their modes of movement, nutrition. Children are introduced to the cubs of some animals. They are given their first knowledge of the distinctive features of the seasons.

In the middle group, children's ideas about the properties and qualities of inanimate objects are expanded and specified (for example, water is a transparent liquid that flows; some objects float in water, others sink; snow and water change their properties depending on the air temperature).

In the senior group, the main task is to form children's knowledge about the connections and relationships that exist in nature: about the needs of plants and animals depending on living conditions and condition, about the connections between some organs and their functions.

In the preparatory group for school, the main task is to clarify and expansion of knowledge about the regular changes in inanimate nature phenomena, their further systematization and generalization. It is necessary to form ideas about the change of seasons, about the increase (or decrease) in the length of day and night, about the regular changes in air temperature, the nature of precipitation.

There are three methods of introducing preschoolers to nature: visual, practical, and verbal.

1. Visual methods include: observation, illustrative material, technical means or an educational screen.

Observation is a purposeful, systematic perception of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world. This is a complex cognitive activity, it involves perception, thinking and speech, requires sustained attention. Depending on the cognitive tasks, the teacher uses different types of observations. Observation is organized when introducing children to plants and animals, weather, the work of adults in nature, they are carried out in classes and on excursions, on walks and in a nature corner.

2. Practical methods

Didactic games - in didactic games, children clarify, consolidate, expand their existing ideas about objects and phenomena of nature, plants and animals. Many games lead children to generalization and classification. games are used - with a ball, games with leaves, seeds, flowers, fruits and vegetables. Board games are widely used, which make it possible to systematize children's knowledge of plants, animals, and inanimate phenomena

3. Verbal methods

The teacher's story - you can tell children stories for different purposes: to expand their knowledge of already familiar phenomena, animals, plants, to introduce new phenomena and facts.

The story must be accompanied by illustrative material - photographs, paintings, filmstrips.

Conversation - there are two types: final and preliminary. The purpose of the preliminary one is to clarify the children's experience in order to establish a connection between the upcoming observation and knowledge. The final conversation is aimed at systematizing and generalizing the facts obtained, concretizing them, consolidating and clarifying them.

Technologies used to introduce children to nature

Modern pedagogical technologies in preschool education are aimed at implementing state standards of preschool education, which define new means, forms, methods used in the practice of pedagogy.

ICT technologies in the "information" age are well studied and are used in the professional activities of teachers:

- This is the selection of illustrative material for classes and for decorating stands, groups.
- This is the selection of additional educational material for classes (presentations, cartoons, etc.)
- This is the exchange of experience (created websites on the Internet, a kindergarten website, familiarization with periodicals, the developments of other teachers in Russia and abroad.
- These are interactive games

The technological approach, that is, new pedagogical technologies, guarantee the achievements of preschoolers and subsequently guarantee their successful education at school.

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